

D3.4 Electric system [DC-box and HV junction box] and UFC verification results

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

The present document shows the development of the demonstrators related with the electrical circuit. This is, the DC-BOX system consisting in a Communication Box and the DC-Filter and the Junction Box, which is the electro-mechanic protection system of the battery system. The demonstrator also includes the CCS2 Charge inlets to allow connection to a real EVSE. The present document also incorporates a summary of the dimensioning of busbar connection between cells performed in an internal workshop during February 2023.

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List of abbreviations

<i>BP</i>	<i>Batteries Packs</i>
<i>CE</i>	<i>Circular Economy</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

The present deliverable has the following objectives:

- Show the process of design and the pictures of the Junction Box (JBOX), an electro-mechanic system designed to split the battery, the charge and the active parts of the eVIL.
- Describe the Communication Box and the DC-Filter that are part of the DCBOX system.
- Describe the simple busbar dimensioning carried out during February Workshop.

1. JUNCTION BOX

1.1 JBOX Architecture, first concept and status

Next figure depicts of the JBOX architecture:

Figure 1. Block architecture of the MARBEL JBOX.

A first design of the JBOX has been circulated throughout the consortium partners (Figure 2). This JBOX is dimensioned to withstand the UFC profiles proposed at Task 3.2. Furthermore, the Junction Box is designed to withstand continuous power of two 200kW engines as proposed at the project requirements. Up to now the concept is being validated through electro-thermal simulations (Figure 3)

Figure 2. Demonstrator of 400V/800V MARBEL JBOX.

Figure 3. Electrothermal simulation model of 400V/800V JBOX.

2. DC BOX

2.1 DC-BOX Architecture and status

Next figure shows the architecture of the DC-Box with its subcomponents. The main development within this demonstrator is the Communication Box which includes, HW, SW, and Mechanical Engineering development. The charging inlet and the DC-filter will be properly dimensioned and acquired externally.

Figure 4. Block architecture of the DC-BOX assembly with the Com.BOX and the filter + charging inlet.

DC-BOX activities started on 2022. Specifically, during the first semester, tasks carried out have been related to architecture definition, boundary definition with other eVIL components, HW and SW-Development. Activities of this task were planned to be finished during year 2022. A trimester delay appeared due to changes in the design of the battery pack systems, such a delay does not affect other tasks or WPs.

1. Communication Box Main Specifications:

- 1.1. Charge management – PLC / Proximity Control
- 1.2. Charging Standards for DC-charge implemented: CCS2,
- 1.3. Charging Standards HW Prepared: CHAdeMO, GB/T, Chaoji & Bid.Charge
- 1.4. Plug and charge development
- 1.5. Wake-up strategies for very low power consumption
- 1.6. Infineon TC3xxx MCU + Qualcomm – PLC

Figure 5. Communication BOX demonstrator

2. DC-Filter Specifications:

Next figure shows the set-up for testing the EVSE Ultra-Fast Charge connectivity.

Figure 6. Depiction of the CCS2 plug test set-up.

3. BUSBARS DIMENSIONING

3.1 Model

Simple model of 4 cells developed in Modelica using OpenModelica IDE.

MARBEL - Simple 4 cells model

Figure 7: Battery module simple electro-thermal model [1]

3.1.1 Cell Parameters:

Figure 8: Cell configuration file

3.1.2 Busbar parameters

Parameters

General
Modifiers

Component

Name: busbar

Class

Path: eMobility_Lib.Busbar.Busbar

Comment:

Parameters

n	<input type="text" value="30"/>	
L	<input type="text" value="0.01"/>	m
H	<input type="text" value="0.004"/>	m
W	<input type="text" value="0.01"/>	m
rho	<input type="text" value="8.9600000000000001"/>	g/cm3 ▾
h	<input type="text" value="5.0"/>	W/(K.m2)
k	<input type="text" value="400"/>	W/(m.K)
C	<input type="text" value="385.0"/>	J/(kg.K)
ro_Cu	<input type="text" value="1.68e-8"/>	Ohm.m
alp_Cu	<input type="text" value="0.004"/>	
eps_Cu	<input type="text" value="0.4"/>	

Figure 9: Busbar Parameters

3.2 Results and comments

Simulated time: 1000s

Heat transfer:

- Considered forced cooling at the cells bottom $h=100\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$
- Busbars self-heating dependent on temperature, cooling by conduction, grey-diffuse radiation and natural convection.

3.2.1 Current through each of the cells

Figure 10: Current across each of the module cells

3.2.2 Power generated at the cell

Figure 11: Power generated at each of the battery cells

From which the bast majority goes to self-heat the cell:

Figure 12: Power self-heating the battery cell

And the rest is cooled by the cooling circuit, see the power that the cooling dissipated from 4 cells:

Figure 13: Cooling circuit power rejection

3.2.3 Busbars power and temperature analysis

3.2.3.1 Temperature at the busbars

Figure 14: Battery busbar temperature rise

No big difference seen in the middle busbar although it carries twice as much current, the heat capacity of the cells allows to absorb this surplus of generated energy.

3.2.3.2 Current at different busbars

Figure 15: Current through series busbars and parallel busbars

See that effectively busbar 1, middle busbar carries twice as much current.

3.2.3.3 Power rejected from the busbars to the cells

Figure 16: Power rejected from the busbars to the cells

See how effectively the power rejected from the central busbars to the cells in contact is 4 times higher, since current is twice as big.

3.2.3.4 Power generated at the busbar

A specific Qconvection and Qradiation of the busbar is not available now. Nevertheless, if we consider that total power generated is $P=V*I$, we can see that for the central busbar, the power generated $P=(4.13459-4.13316)*320= 0.4576W$.

pin_n		
<input type="checkbox"/> i	-320	A
<input type="checkbox"/> v	4.13316	V
pin_p		
<input type="checkbox"/> i	320	A
<input type="checkbox"/> v	4.13459	V

Considering that the heat flowing from the central is 0.2W (see previous picture) and that the busbar is connected to two cells. 0.4W goes to the cells and 0.0576W is cooled by means of natural convection + radiation.

3.2.4 SOC at the cells

Figure 17: State of Charge evolution of cells

3.2.5 Cells temperature

Figure 18: Cells temperature evolution

The value of the simulation is consistent with experimental data of cell tests.

3.2.6 Busbar temperature

Figure 19: Cell module busbar temperature rise

Temperature at the busbars terminals is mainly controlled by the inertia of the cell behaviour thus remaining low during charge.

3.3 Cooling circuit pre-dimensioning

In order to determine the cooling power of the cooling circuit, three charge and discharge cycles have been reproduced.

Figure 20: Temperature at the busbar after three charge-drive cycles

In terms of cooling energy this means for 4 cells we should ensure the following cooling power:

Figure 21: Module cooling power to ensure the previous temperature cycling

Multiplied by the total amount of cells, this means that the cooling should be able to extract minimum 2880W from the battery. This, I believe, it's a normal value.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present document presents the electrical system demonstrators and briefly explains its design. The deliverable also includes information about a simple validation of busbar cross-section design and cooling circuit design. Next steps in MARBEL project are related to the integration of this components in the eVIL (WP6).

5. Bibliography

- [1] S. E. M. Hilding Elmqvist, «MODELICA — THE NEXT GENERATION MODELING LANGUAGE,» *Proceedings1 of the 1st World Congress on System Simulation (WCSS'97)*, 1997.